

THE CONTENT OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF
DEVELOPING MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE
PEDAGOGUES IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10947291>

Abstract: This article describes the application of the credit module system in the educational process and the development of management competencies of future pedagogues in the credit module system.

Key words: Credit module system, pedagogue, educational process, educational organization.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the principle of credit module, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating.

The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- evaluation of students' knowledge based on the rating score;
- to enable students to create their own study plans individually;
- increasing the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the convenience of educational programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

Now we will consider the management competencies of the future teacher in the credit module system.

Processes of training highly qualified pedagogic personnel that meet the requirements of the time are currently the main demand of the international labor market. The reason for this is that free-thinking, self-expressive, and objectively self-assessed people are very important in society.

They are the movers of the development of society. This, in its place, makes a great contribution to the development of the professional competence of specialists and renews the content of education, bringing about the need for the wide implementation of innovative forms and methods of teaching, advanced foreign experiences in teaching modern information and communication technologies. In this regard, a number of measures are

currently being implemented in educational institutions to further improve the quality of education, to ensure the coherence and continuity of educational courses. In addition, the concept of competence is also important in the characteristics of the development of professional competence in future pedagogues. Competence - requires constant enrichment of one's knowledge and skills, learning new information, feeling the demands of the current era, the ability to find new knowledge, process it and apply it during one's work. It is worth noting that the modernization of the educational process in educational institutions, the improvement of the professional competence of pedagogues in the further improvement of the quality level of the system of training of pedagogues, their professional knowledge, skills and experience using modern advanced foreign experiences in the field One of the important tasks is to arm with skills, to be able to independently use scientific and technical innovations, and to further develop the skills to solve promising tasks. In this regard, it is an important task to pay special attention to the professional competence of future teachers and their analytical skills.

Today, the term "professional competence" is often used. Dictionaries define competence as understanding and knowledge. Translated from Latin, "competentia" means a number of matters in which a person is knowledgeable, has knowledge and experience. Latin: *competo* - to reach, to obey, to approach. In a word, professional competence is the ability to translate knowledge, skills and abilities into practice. Professional competencies are the ability to perform professional tasks or a specific professional task. It is assumed that you will be able to perform the work effectively and achieve the desired result.

The following types of competence are also distinguished:

- individual competence: personal characteristics that help you promote yourself and achieve results.
- leadership skills: leadership, not management. Because not all leaders can be leaders, just as not all leaders can be leaders. It refers more to the extent to which a person can lead or guide the development of a person and a professional.
- functional competencies. It refers only to the field of human activity.
- social competence: includes cognitive and behavioral skills within a social group.
- emotional competence: the ability to analyze your strengths and weaknesses, for which emotional intelligence is responsible.

Developing the professional competence of today's teacher is to increase his daily ability and productivity of the work process. It is possible to train qualified specialists by studying and solving problems related to the formation of professional skills in work, forming professional training. The need to improve pedagogical and psychological knowledge and skills of future teachers is based on the growth of social demands placed on educational institutions and teachers. In the field of higher education, determination of the actual needs for education is carried out based on the determination of the level of their professional training, the aspects that meet the requirements, as well as the existing shortcomings and gaps. Based on this, it is appropriate to implement innovations. This leads to the development of pedagogical competence. Another important situation during training sessions is to organize the educational processes of students based on their needs and to focus on the personality of the student. These include methods of forming students' interest in learning, their sense of duty and responsibility in the educational process. Organization and development of collaborative work of subjects in the further improvement of pedagogical processes, the effectiveness of developing their activity in the system of goals and tasks that are important to achieve, is inextricably dependent on existing motives and motivation.

The field of education is a social institution that reflects all the problems of society. In modern education, it is necessary to enrich and improve spiritual and educational values, to humanize it through educational activities, to activate educational activities with spiritual and educational growth, to provide pedagogical and psychological support. It is necessary to educate highly moral, responsible, creative, competent persons through support. Raising a person from the spiritual and educational side is an important issue of education today, and for this it is important that the teacher himself has a high level of spiritual and educational competence.

Scientific activity of teachers - searching for news, learning and basing on them and using scientifically proven sources, mastering the pedagogical, psychological and socio-economic bases of organizing and managing pedagogical processes, as well as applying innovative approach technologies to pedagogical processes defines tasks.

In conclusion, we must say that introducing future teachers to various methods and methods of organizing and managing pedagogical processes, further developing their professional competence, arming them with the secrets of professional development, and forming a methodology for working with

pedagogical innovations will increase the effectiveness of education. is one of the important increasing factors. In order to ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical processes, future teachers should have knowledge of strategic planning, design, modeling of pedagogical processes, coordination of student activities and ensuring their activity, methods, methods and principles of pedagogical process management according to situations, innovative technologies and based on them, it is necessary to develop the skills of organizing innovative activities of the subjects of the pedagogical process.

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